

Task 9.1. Questionnaire to expand and consolidate the European network of HBM laboratories

The Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) is a European project that involves close to 200 institutions from 28 countries, the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the European Environment Agency (EEA). PARC aims to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment. It supports the European Union's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the European Green Deal's "Zero pollution" ambition with new data, knowledge, methods and tools, expertise, and networks.

In PARC, WP9 "Building infrastructural and human capacities" focuses on promoting of the development of existing and new infrastructural and human capacities related to laboratory networks. Under task 9.1, we are working to expand and consolidate the European Network of HBM laboratories created in HBM4EU, and for that, we kindly ask you for your collaboration. The questionnaire should be completed by ALL LABORATORIES, those already in the network for updating purposes and new laboratories to be included in the network.

For those laboratories interested in participating in the analysis of HBM samples within PARC, please be aware that by joining this network you will automatically receive information about the PARC Quality Assurance/Quality Control programme (QA/QC programme) from WP4, task 4.1.2. Successful participation in this programme will be a requisite to perform HBM chemical analyses in PARC.

Additionally, the information collected from this questionnaire will contribute to strengthening capacities and laboratory procedures within task 9.3.

Please, complete the questionnaire before the **8th September 2023**.

If you have any problem or question, do not hesitate to contact us at PARC@isciii.es.

<https://researchsurvey.limequery.com/348873?lang=en>

PARC

1. Contact details

Question	Answer
1.1 Are you a member of PARC?	Yes/No
1.1.1 Please specify your acronym and number in PARC	
1.2 Laboratory/Department name:	
1.3 Address (street name, number, postal code, city):	
1.4 Country:	
1.5 Contact person name:	
1.6 Contact person email:	

2. Experience in chemical analysis

Divided in different independent subsections for each group of compounds:

1. Per-and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)
2. Phthalates and substitutes
3. Metals and trace elements
4. Flame retardants
5. Bisphenols
6. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)
7. Cotinine
8. Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)
9. Acrylamide
10. Mycotoxins
11. Pesticides-pyrethroids
12. Pesticides-organophosphorus
13. Pesticides-phenylpyrazole
14. Pesticides-glyphosate
15. Pesticides-organochlorine
16. Pesticides-neonicotinoids
17. Pesticides-others
18. Aprotic solvents
19. UV filters-benzophenones
20. Diisocyanates
21. Aromatic amines
22. Parabens
23. Dioxins and Furans
24. Musks
25. Other chemicals

2. Experience in chemical analysis

For each of these groups of compounds the questions are:

2.1. Do you have experience with X (chemical group)?

Select	Yes
Select	No

(goes to next chemical group)

If yes,

For X (chemical group), please consider the following questions:

2.2. Please indicate in which human matrices you have experience in analysing X (chemical group).

Please choose:

Adipose tissue
Breast milk
Cord blood
Faeces
Dried blood spot samples (DBS)
Hair
Meconium
Nails
Placenta
Plasma
Saliva
Semen
Serum
Urine
Volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMs)
Whole blood
Other, please specify

2. Experience in chemical analysis

2.3. Please indicate the instrumental technique employed.

Please choose:

AAS
CV-AAS
CV-AFS
Direct Mercury Analyser
ELISA
GC-FPD
GC-HRMS
GC-MS
GC-MS/MS
GC-NPD
GF-AAS
HG-AAS
IC-ICP-MS
ICP-DRC-MS
ICP-AES
ICP-MS
LC-FLD
LC-HRMS
LC-ICP-MS
LC-MS/MS
Other, please specify

2.4. Please indicate the sample amount required.

Sample amount	Sample amount units
	<i>Please choose:</i> <i>mg</i> <i>g</i> <i>mL</i> <i>μL</i>

2. Experience in chemical analysis

2.5. Please indicate the biomarkers you analyse (please do not forget to include the LOQ and units, this information is very important).

Tables with all the information requested can be found at the end of this section

2.5.1 Do you analyse any other biomarkers for PFAS (in addition to those listed above)?

Select	Yes
Select	No

If yes,

2.5.2 Please indicate the other biomarkers you analyse and the LOQ.

Name	CAS	LOQ	LOQ units

2.6. Do you employ other instrumental technique for this group of substances?

Biomarker name	CAS	Instrumental technique	Sample amount	Sample amount units	LOQ	LOQ units

2.7. Do you analyse this group of substances in other matrices?

Select	Yes
Select	No

Submit and go to next chemical group

If yes,

Please indicate in which other human matrices you have experience in analysing X (chemical group)

Please choose: Adipose tissue
 Breast milk

2. Experience in chemical analysis

Please choose (cont.):

Cord blood
Faeces
Dried blood spot samples (DBS)
Hair
Meconium
Nails
Placenta
Plasma
Saliva
Semen
Serum
Urine
Volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMs)
Whole blood
Other, please specify

Fill in same questions as above 2.3-2.7

2. Experience in chemical analysis

1. PFAS

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
ADONA (Ammonium 4,8-dioxa-3H-perfluorononanoate)	919005-14-4			
C6/C6 PFPiA (Bis(perfluorohexyl)phosphinic acid)	40143-77-9			
C6/C8 PFPiA (Bis(perfluorohexyloctyl)phosphinic acid)	610800-34-5			
C8/C8 PFPiA (Bis(perfluorooctyl)phosphinic acid)	40143-79-1			
EtFOSAA (N-ethyl-perfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetate)				
EtFOSE (N-Ethyl-perfluorooctane sulphonamidoethanol)	1691-99-2			
FBSA (Perfluorobutane sulfonamide)	30334-69-1			
FOSA (Perfluoro-1-octaperfluoro-1-octanesulphonamide)	754-91-6			
GenX (Ammonium 2,3,3,3-tetrafluoro-2-(heptafluoropropoxy)propanoate)	13252-13-6			
MeFOSAA (N-methyl-perfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetate)	2355-31-9			
MeFOSE (N-Methyl-perfluorooctane sulphonamidoethanol)	24448-09-7			
N-EtFOSA (N-Ethylperfluoro-1-octanesulphonamide)	4151-50-2			
N-MeFOSA (N-Methylperfluoro-1-octanesulphonamide)	31506-32-8			
PFBA (Perfluorobutanoic acid)	375-22-4			
PFBS (Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid)	375-73-5			
PFDA (Perfluorodecanoic acid)	335-76-2			
PFDoDA (Perfluorododecanoic acid)	307-55-1			
PFDPA (Perfluorodecylphosphonic acid)	52299-26-0			
PFDS (Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid)	335-77-3			
PFECHS (Perfluoro-4-ethylcyclohexane sulfonate)	646-83-3			
PFHpA (Perfluoroheptanoic acid)	375-85-9			
PFHpS (Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid)	60270-55-5			
PFHxA (Perfluorohexanoic acid)	307-24-4			
PFHxDA (Perfluorohexadecanoic acid)	67905-19-5			
PFHxPA (Perfluorohexylphosphonic acid)	40143-76-8			
PFHxS (Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid)	355-46-4			
PFNA (Perfluorononanoic acid)	375-95-1			
PFOA (Perfluorooctanoic acid)	335-67-1			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

1. PFAS

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
PFODA (Perfluorooctadecanoic acid)	16517-11-6			
PFOPA (Perfluorooctylphosphonic acid)	252237-40-4			
PFOS (Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid)	1763-23-1			
PFPeA (Perfluoropentanoic acid)	2706-90-3			
PFPrA (Perfluoropropionic acid)	422-64-0			
PFTeDA (Perfluorotetradecanoic acid)	376-06-7			
PFTrDA (Perfluorotridecanoic acid)	72629-94-8			
PFTrS (Perfluorotrisulfonate)				
PFUnDA (Perfluoroundecanoic acid)	2058-94-8			
TFA (Trifluoroacetic acid)	76-05-1			
4:2 FTSA (4:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid)	757124-72-4			
5:3 FTCA (5:3 Fluorotelomer carboxylic acid)	914637-49-3			
6:2 diPAP (6:2 Polyfluoroalkyl phosphoric acid diesters)	57677-95-9			
6:2 FTCA (6:2 Fluorotelomer carboxylic acid)	53826-12-3			
6:2 FTSA (6:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid)	27619-97-2			
6:2 FTUCA (6:2 Fluorotelomer unsaturated carboxylic acid)	70887-88-6			
6:2 monoPAP (6:2 Polyfluoroalkyl phosphoric acid monoesters)	57678-01-0			
7:3 FTCA (7:3 Fluorotelomer carboxylic acid)	812-70-4			
8:2 diPAP (8:2 Polyfluoroalkyl phosphoric acid diesters)	678-41-1			
8:2 FTCA (8:2 Fluorotelomer carboxylic acid)	27854-31-5			
8:2 FTOH (8:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol)	678-39-7			
8:2 FTSA (8:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid)	39108-34-4			
8:2 FTUCA (8:2 Fluorotelomer unsaturated carboxylic acid)	70887-84-2			
8:2 monoPAP (8:2 Polyfluoroalkyl phosphoric acid monoesters)	57678-03-2			
10:2 FTCA (10:2 Fluorotelomer carboxylic acid)	53826-13-4			
10:2 FTUCA (10:2 Fluorotelomer unsaturated carboxylic acid)	70887-94-4			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

2. Phthalates and substitutes

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
cx-MiDP (Mono-carboxy-isodecyl phthalate)				
cx-MINCH, MCOCH (Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-carboxylate-4-methyl)heptyl ester)	1637562-51-6			
cx-MiNP, MCOP, MCiOP (7-Carboxy-(mono-methyl- heptyl) phthalate/ Mono-carboxy-isononyl phthalate, Mono-4-methyl-7-carboxyheptyl phthalate)	936022-02-5			
cx-MPHP, MCNP (Mono(2,7-methyl-7-carboxy-heptyl) phthalate/Mono-(2-propyl-6-carboxyhexyl) phthalate)				
cx-MPHxP (Mono(2-propyl-6-carboxyhexyl) phthalate)	1412411-10-9			
MBzP (Mono-benzyl phthalate)	2528-16-7			
MCHP (Mono-cyclo-hexyl phthalate)	7517-36-4			
MCHpP/cx-MHpP (Mono-carboxy-n-heptyl phthalate)	856869-57-3			
MCMHP, 2cx-MMHP (Mono(2-carboxymethylhexyl) phthalate)	82975-93-7			
MEHA (Mono(2-ethylhexyl) adipate)	4337-65-9			
MEP (Mono-ethyl phthalate)	2306-33-4			
MEHP (Mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate)	4376-20-9			
MEHTP (1-Mono-(2-ethylhexyl) terephthalate)	155603-50-2			
MiBP (Mono-isobutyl phthalate)	30833-53-5			
MiDP (Mono-isodecyl phthalate)	31047-64-0			
MINCH (Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid-mono(isononyl) ester)				
MiNP (Mono-iso-nonyl phthalate / Mono-methyl-octyl phthalate)	1332965-96-4			
MiPeP (Mono-isopentyl phthalate)	776297-69-9			
MiPrP (Mono-iso-propyl phthalate)	35118-50-4			
MMP (Mono-methyl phthalate)	4376-18-5			
MnBP (Mono-n-butyl phthalate)	131-70-4			
MnHpP (Mono-n-heptyl phthalate)	129171-03-5			
MnHxP (Mono-n-hexyl phthalate)	24539-57-9			
MnOP, MOP (Mono-n-octyl phthalate)	5393-19-1			
MnPeP, MPP (Mono-n-pentyl phthalate / monopentyl phthalate)	24539-56-8			
MnPrP (Mono-n-propyl phthalate)	4376-19-6			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

2. Phthalates and substitutes

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
Mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) adipate	134998-71-3			
Mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) adipate	134998-72-4			
Mono(2-propyl-6-hydroxyheptyl) phthalate	1372605-11-2			
Mono(2-propylheptyl) phthalate				
Mono(4-hydroxypentyl) phthalate	1334312-05-8			
Mono(7-carboxy-n-hexyl) phthalate				
MPHP (Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate)				
OH-MiBP (2-OH-Mono-iso-butylphthalate)	64339-39-5			
OH-MiDP, MHiDP (6-OH-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate)	1372605-11-2			
OH-MINCH, MHNCH (Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-hydroxy-4-methyl)octyl ester)	1637562-52-7			
OH-MiNP, MHNP (7-OH-(Mono-methyl-octyl) phthalate, Mono-hydroxy-isononyl phthalate)	898544-10-0			
OH-MnBP, MHBP (3-OH-Mono-n-butyl phthalate, mono-(3-hydroxybutyl) phthalate)	57074-43-8			
OH-MnPrP (Mono-n-hydroxy-propyl phthalate)				
OH-MPHP (6-OH-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate)	1372605-11-2			
oxo-MiDP, MOiDP (6-Oxo-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate)	1373125-92-8			
oxo-MINCH, MONCH (Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate-mono-(7-oxo-4-methyl)octyl ester)	1588520-62-0			
oxo-MiNP, MONP (7-Oxo-(Mono-methyl-octyl) phthalate)	936022-00-3			
oxo-MnPrP (Mono(2-propyl-6-oxoheptyl) phthalate)	1373125-92-8			
oxo-MPHP (6-Oxo-Mono-propyl-heptyl phthalate)				
1-Mono-(2-carboxyl-methyl-hexyl) benzene-1,4-dicarboxylate				
1-Mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxyl-pentyl) benzene-1,4-dicarboxylate				
1-Mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxy-hexyl) benzene-1,4-dicarboxylate				
1-Mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxo-hexyl) benzene-1,4-dicarboxylate				
1-MEHTM (1-Mono-(2-ethylhexyl) trimellitate)				
1,4 DEHTM (1,4-Di-(2-ethylhexyl) trimellitate)				
2-MEHTM (2-mono-(2-ethylhexyl) trimellitate)				
2cx-2-MMHTM (2-mono-(2-carboxymethylhexyl) trimellitate)				

2. Experience in chemical analysis

2. Phthalates and substitutes

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
2cx-1-MMHTM (1-mono-(2-carboxymethylhexyl) trimellitate)				
2,4 DEHTM (2,4-Di-(2-ethylhexyl) trimellitate)				
3-carboxyl-mono-propyl phthalate, mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate	66851-46-5			
3OH-MiPeP (3-hydroxy-monoisopentyl phthalate)				
4-MEHTM (4-mono-(2-ethylhexyl) trimellitate)				
4OH-MiPeP (4-hydroxy-monoisopentyl phthalate)				
5cx-MEPA (Mono-5-carboxy-2-ethylpentyl adipate)				
5cx-MEPP, MECPP (Mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxy- pentyl) phthalate)	40809-41-4			
5cx-MEPTP (Mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) terephthalate)	1684398-42-2			
5cx-1-MEPTM (1-mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) trimellitate)				
5cx-2-MEPTM (2-mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) trimellitate)				
5cx-MnPeP (Mono-(5-carboxy-n-pentyl) phthalate)	92569-49-8			
5OH-MEHA (Mono-2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl adipate)	134998-71-3			
5OH-MEHP, MEHHP (Mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxy-hexyl) phthalate)	40321-99-1			
5OH-MEHTP (Mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) terephthalate)	1684398-38-6			
5OH-MnHexP (Mono-(5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate)				
5OH-1-MEHTM (1-mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) trimellitate)				
5OH-2-MEHTM (2-mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) trimellitate)				
5oxo-MEHP, MEOHP (Mono(2-ethyl-5-oxo-hexyl) phthalate)	40321-98-0			
5oxo-1-MEHTM (1-mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) trimellitate)				
5oxo-2-MEHTM (2-mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) trimellitate)				
6OH-MHpP (Mono-(6-hydroxyheptyl) phthalate)				

2. Experience in chemical analysis

3. Metals and trace elements

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Antimony	7440-36-0			
Arsenic (total)	7440-38-2			
Arsenic (III)	22541-54-4			
Arsenic (V)	17428-41-0			
Inorganic Arsenic (As(III) + As (V))				
Dimethylarsinic acid (DMA)	75-60-5			
Monomethylarsonic acid (MMA)	124-58-3			
Sum As(III) + As(V) + DMA + MMA				
Arsenobetaine (AsB)	64436-13-1			
Barium	7440-39-3			
Cadmium	7440-43-9			
Chromium (total)	7440-47-3			
Chromium (Cr (III))	16065-83-1			
Chromium (Cr (VI))	18540-29-9			
Cobalt	7440-48-4			
Lead	7439-92-1			
Manganese	7439-96-5			
Mercury (total)	7439-97-6			
Mercury (inorganic)				
Methylmercury	22967-92-6			
Molybdenum	7439-98-7			
Strontium	7440-24-6			
Thallium	7440-28-0			
Tin	7440-31-5			
Tungsten	7440-33-7			
Uranium	7440-61-1			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

4. Flame retardants

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
Anti-dechlorane plus	135821-74-8			
BH-TEBP (Bis(2-ethylhexyl)-3,4,5,6-tetrabromophthalate)	26040-51-7			
Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate	789440-10-4			
Bis(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate	72236-72-7			
Bis(2-butoxyethyl) 3'-hydroxy-2-butoxyethyl phosphate	1477494-87-3			
Bis(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate	14260-97-0			
Bis(2-chloroethyl) phosphate	3040-56-0			
BTBPE (1,2 bis(2,4,6-tribromophenoxy)ethane)	37853-59-1			
DBDPE (Decabromodiphenylethane)	84852-53-9			
Dechlorane 602	31107-44-5			
Dechlorane 603	13560-92-4			
Dechlorane 604	34571-16-9			
Di-n-butyl phosphate	107-66-4			
Diphenyl phosphate	838-85-7			
DP/DDC-CO (Dechlorane Plus)	13560-89-9			
EH-TBB (2-ethylhexyl-2,3,4,5-tetrabromobenzoate)	183658-27-7			
HBB (Hexabromobenzene)	87-82-1			
HCDBCO/DBHCTD (Hexachlorocyclopentadienyl-dibromocyclooctane)	51936-55-1			
Hexabromocyclododecane (total)	3194-55-6			
Hydroxyphenyl diphenyl phosphate	56806-74-7			
i,p-TPP (Isopropyl triphenyl phosphate)	68937-41-7			
OBIND/OBTMPI (Octabromotrimethylphenylindane)	155613-93-7			
PBB-Acr (Pentabromobenzyl acrylate)	59447-55-1			
PBEB (Pentabromoethylbenzene)	85-22-3			
PBDE 28 (2,4,4'-Tribromodiphenyl ether)	41318-75-6			
PBDE 47 (2,2',4,4'-Tetrabromodiphenyl ether)	5436-43-1			
PBDE 66 (2,3',4,4'-Tetrabromodiphenyl ether)	189084-61-5			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

4. Flame retardants

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
PBDE 71 (2,3',4',6-Tetrabromodiphenyl ether)	189084-62-6			
PBDE 75 (2,4,4',6-Tetrabromodiphenyl ether)	189084-63-7			
PBDE 77 (3,3',4,4'-Tetrabromodiphenyl ether)	93703-48-1			
PBDE 85 (2,2',3,4,4'-Pentabromodiphenyl ether)	182346-21-0			
PBDE 99 (2,2',4,4',5-Pentabromodiphenyl ether)	60348-60-9			
PBDE 100 (2,2',4,4',6-Pentabromodiphenyl ether)	89084-64-8			
PBDE 119 (2,3',4,4',6-Pentabromodiphenyl ether)	189084-66-0			
PBDE 138 (2,2',3,4,4',5'-Hexabromodiphenyl ether)	182677-30-1			
PBDE 153 (2,2',4,4',5,5'-Hexabromodiphenyl ether)	68631-49-2			
PBDE 154 (2,2',4,4',5,6'-Hexabromodiphenyl ether)	207122-15-4			
PBDE 182 (2,2',3,4,4',5',6-Heptabromodiphenyl ether)	182677-30-1			
PBDE 183 (2,2',4,4',5,5',6-Heptabromodiphenyl ether)	207122-16-5			
PBDE 190 (2,3,3',4,4',5,6-Heptabromodiphenyl ether)	189084-68-2			
PBDE 209 (Decabromodiphenyl ether)	1163-19-5			
PBT (Pentabromotoluene)	87-83-2			
Pentabromophenol	608-71-9			
Perchloropentacyclodecane	2385-85-5			
Syn-dechlorane plus	135821-03-3			
TBBPA (Tetrabromobisphenol A)	79-94-7			
TBECH/DBE-DBCH (Tetrabromoethylcyclohexane)	3322-93-8			
TBOEP (Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate)	78-51-3			
TBX (2,3,5,6-tetrabromo-p-xylene)	23488-38-2			
TCEP (Tris(2-chloroethyl) phosphate)	115-96-8			
TCIPP (Tris(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate)	13674-84-5			
TDClPP (Tris(1,3-dichloropropyl)phosphate)	40120-74-9			
TEHP (Tris(2-ethylhexyl) phosphate)	78-42-2			
TEP (Triethyl phosphate)	78-40-0			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

4. Flame retardants

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
TMPP (Tricresyl phosphate)	1330-78-5			
TNBP (Tri-n-butyl phosphate)	126-73-8			
TPHP (Triphenyl phosphate)	115-86-6			
Tris(2,3-dibromopropyl) phosphate	126-72-7			
Tris(chloroethyl) phosphate	115-96-8			
1-Hydroxy-2propyl bis (1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate	1477495-11-6			
1,2,2,2-tetrabromoethylcyclohexane	3322-93-8			
1,2,5,6-Tetrabromocyclooctane	3194-57-8			
2-Ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl diphenyl phosphate	2173149-33-0			
2-Ethylhexyl phenyl phosphate	20403-99-0			
2-Hydroxyethyl bis(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate	1477494-86-2			
2,3,4,5-Tetrabromo benzoic acid	98-73-7			
2,4,6-Tribromophenol	118-79-6			
2,4-Dibromophenol	615-58-7			
4-hydroxyphenyl phenyl phosphate	114527-61-6			
Hydroxylated metabolites, please specify				
Methoxylated metabolites, please specify				
α-HBCDD (Hexabromocyclododecane alpha)	134237-50-6			
β-HBCDD (Hexabromocyclododecane beta)	134237-51-7			
γ-HBCDD (Hexabromocyclododecane gamma)	134237-52-8			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

5. Bisphenols

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
BPA Total (Bisphenol A total)	80-05-7			
BPA Unconjugated (Bisphenol A free)				
BPA Conjugated (Bisphenol A conjugated)				
BPAF (4,4-(Hexafluoro-isopropylidene)-diphenol)	1478-61-1			
BPAP (4,4-(1-Phenyl-ethylidene)-bisphenol)	260550-89-8			
BPB (2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)butane)	77-40-7			
BPBP (2,2-Bis(2-hydroxy-5-biphenyl)propane)	24038-68-4			
BPC (4,4'-Isopropylidenedi-o-cresol)	79-97-0			
BPE (4,4'-Ethylidene bisphenol)	2081-08-5			
BPF Total (Bisphenol F total)	620-92-8			
BPF Unconjugated (Bisphenol F free)				
BPF Conjugated (Bisphenol F conjugated)				
BPG (2,2-Bis(4-hydroxy-3-isopropylphenyl)propane)	127-54-8			
BPM (4,4'-(1,3-Phenylene-bis(1-methylethylidene)) bisphenol)	13595-25-0			
BPP (4,4'-(1,4-Phenylenediisopropylidene) bisphenol)	2167-51-3			
BPS Total (Bisphenol S total)	80-09-1			
BPS Unconjugated (Bisphenol S free)				
BPS Conjugated (Bisphenol S conjugated)				
BPZ (4,4'-Cyclo-hexylidene bisphenol)	843-55-0			
2,2-BPF (2,2'-Bisphenol F)	2467-02-9			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

6. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
ACE (Acenaphthene)	83-32-9			
ACY (Acenaphthylene)	208-96-8			
AN (Anthracene)	120-12-7			
BaA (Benz[a]anthracene)	56-55-3			
BaP (Benzo[a]pyrene)	50-32-8			
BbFA (Benzo[b]fluoranthene)	205-99-2			
BcFL (Benzo[c]fluorene)	205-12-9			
BcPh (Benzo[c]phenanthrene)	195-19-7			
BeP (Benzo[e]pyrene)	192-97-2			
BghiP (Benzo[g,h,i]perylene)	191-24-2			
BjFA (Benzo[j]fluoranthene)	205-82-3			
BkFA (Benzo[k]fluoranthene)	207-08-9			
CPP (Cyclopenta[c,d]pyrene)	27208-37-3			
CRY (Chrysene)	218-01-9			
DBaeP (Dibenzo[a,e]pyrene)	192-65-4			
DBahA (Dibenzo[a,h]anthracene)	53-70-3			
DBaiP (Dibenzo[a,i]pyrene)	189-55-9			
DBaIP (Dibenzo[a,l]pyrene)	191-30-0			
DMBA (7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene)	57-97-6			
FLA (Fluoranthene)	206-44-0			
FLUO (Fluorene)	86-73-7			
IP (Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene)	193-39-5			
NAPH (Naphthalene)	91-20-3			
PHE (Phenanthrene)	85-01-8			
Phenanthrene-1,2,3,4-tetrol				
PYR (Pyrene)	129-00-0			
1-BaA (1-Hydroxybenz[a]anthracene)	69847-26-3			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

6. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
1-CRY (1-Hydroxychrysene)	63019-38-5			
1-Hydroxyphenanthrene	2433-56-9			
1-Methylphenanthrene	832-69-9			
1-Naphthol (1-Hydroxynaphthalene)	90-15-3			
1-PYR (1-Hydroxypyrene)	5315-79-7			
1,2-Dihydrophenanthrene-1,2-diol	28622-66-4			
1,2-Dihydroxynaphthalene	574-00-5			
2-FLUO (2-Hydroxyfluorene)	2443-58-5			
2-Hydroxyphenanthrene	605-55-0			
2-Naphthol (2-Hydroxynaphthalene)	135-19-3			
2,3,5-TMNPT (2,3,5-Trimethylnaphthalene)	2245-38-7			
2,6-Dimethylnaphthalene	581-42-0			
3-BCP (3-Hydroxybenzo[c]-phenanthrene)	22717-95-9			
3-FLUO (3-Hydroxyfluorene)	6344-67-8			
3-Hydroxyphenanthrene	605-87-8			
3-Hydroxybenzo(a)pyrene	13345-21-6			
4-Hydroxyphenanthrene	7651-86-7			
6-CRY (6-Hydroxychrysene)	37515-51-8			
9-FLUO (9-Hydroxyfluorene)	1689-64-1			
9-Hydroxyphenanthrene	484-17-3			
9,10-Phenanthrenediol	604-84-2			
α -Methylnaphthalene (1-Methylnaphthalene)	90-12-0			
β -Methylnaphthalene (2-Methylnaphthalene)	91-57-6			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

7. Cotinine

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Cotinine	486-56-6			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

8. Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
PCB 28 (2,4-Dichloro-1-(4-chlorophenyl)benzene)	7012-37-5			
PCB 52 (1,4-Dichloro-2-(2,5-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	32598-13-3			
PCB 77 (1,2-Dichloro-4-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	70362-50-4			
PCB 81 (1,2,3-Trichloro-5-(4-chlorophenyl)benzene)	57465-28-8			
PCB 101 (1,2,4-Trichloro-5-(2,5-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	35693-99-3			
PCB 103 (1,3,5-Trichloro-2-(2,5-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	60145-21-3			
PCB 105 (1,2,3-Trichloro-4-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	37680-73-2			
PCB 114 (1,2,3,4-Tetrachloro-5-(4-chlorophenyl)benzene)	35065-28-2			
PCB 118 (1,2,4-Trichloro-5-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	35065-27-1			
PCB 123 (1,2,3-Trichloro-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	35065-29-3			
PCB 126 (1,2,3-Trichloro-5-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	32774-16-6			
PCB 138 (1,2,3-Trichloro-4-(2,4,5-trichlorophenyl)benzene)	65510-44-3			
PCB 153 (1,2,4-Trichloro-5-(2,4,5-trichlorophenyl)benzene)	31508-00-6			
PCB 156 (1,2,3,4-Tetrachloro-5-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)benzene)	74472-37-0			
PCB 157 (1,2,3-Trichloro-4-(3,4,5-trichlorophenyl)benzene)	32598-14-4			
PCB 167 (1,2,3-Trichloro-5-(2,4,5-trichlorophenyl)benzene)	52663-72-6			
PCB 169 (1,2,3-Trichloro-5-(3,4,5-trichlorophenyl)benzene)	38380-08-4			
PCB 180 (1,2,3,4-Tetrachloro-5-(2,4,5-trichlorophenyl)benzene)	69782-90-7			
PCB 189 (1,2,3,4-Tetrachloro-5-(3,4,5-trichlorophenyl)benzene)	39635-31-9			
Hydroxylated metabolites, please specify				
Methoxylated metabolites, please specify				

2. Experience in chemical analysis

9. Acrylamide

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL
AAMA (N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoyl-ethyl)cysteine)	81690-92-8			
AAVal (N-(2-Carbamoylethyl)valine)	51078-53-6			
GAMA (N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl)cysteine)	137698-08-9			
GAVal (N-(2-Carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl)valine)	252663-74-4			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

10. Mycotoxins

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
AFB1 (Aflatoxin B1)	1162-65-8			
AFB-lysine				
AFB-N7-guanine	79982-94-8			
AFM1 (Aflatoxin M1)	6795-23-9			
Deepoxy-deoxynivalenol	88054-24-4			
Deoxynivalenol-free	51481-10-8			
Deoxynivalenol-total	51481-10-8			
Deoxynivalenol-15-acetate	88337-96-6			
Deoxynivalenol-3-glucoside	131180-21-7			
Deoxynivalenol-15-glucuronide	1372859-16-9			
Deoxynivalenol-3-glucuronide	1000000-13-4			
FB1 (Fumonisin B1)	116355-83-0			
3-Acetyldeoxynivalenol	50722-38-8			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

11. Pesticides-pyrethroids

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Acrinathrin	101007-06-1			
Allethrin	584-79-2			
Allethrin	584-79-2			
Bifenthrin	82657-04-3			
Chlorotrifluorovinylcyclo-propane carboxylic acid (or cis-3-[2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl]-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid)	68127-59-3			
Cis-3-(2,2-dibromovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid	63597-73-9			
Cis-DCCA (Cis-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid)	55667-40-8			
ClF3CA (Cis-3-(2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid)	68127-59-3			
Cyfluthrin	68359-37-5			
Cyphenothrin	39515-40-7			
Cypermethrin	52315-07-8			
DBCA (Cis-(2,2-dibromovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid)	59952-39-5			
Deltamethrin	52918-63-5			
d-Tetramethrin	1166-46-7			
Empenthrin	54406-48-3			
Epsilonomflurothrin	1065124-65-3			
Esfenvalerate	66230-04-4			
Etofenprox	80844-07-1			
Fenpropathrin	39515-41-8			
Fenvalerate	51630-58-1			
Imiprothrin	72963-72-5			
Metofluthrin	240494-70-6			
Permethrin	52645-53-1			
Phenothrin	26002-80-2			
Prallethrin	23031-36-9			
Resmethrin	10453-86-8			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

11. Pesticides-pyrethroids

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Tau-fluvalinate	102851-06-9			
Tefluthrin	79538-32-2			
Tetramethrin	7696-12-0			
Trans-CDCA (Trans-Chrysanthemumdicarboxylic acid)	497-95-0			
Trans-DCCA (Trans-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid)	55701-03-6			
Transfluthrin	118712-89-3			
1R-transphenothrin	26046-85-5			
3PBA (3-Phenoxybenzoic acid)	3739-38-6			
4-Chloro-alpha-isopropyl benzene acetic acid, (or 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-methylbutyric acid)	2012-74-0			
4F3PBA (4-Fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid)	77279-89-1			
α -Cypermethrin	65731-84-2			
γ -Cyhalothrin	76703-65-6			
λ -Cyhalothrin	91465-08-6			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

12. Pesticides-organophosphorus

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Azinphos-methyl	86-50-0			
ACEP (Acephate)	30560-19-1			
CMHC (3-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)	6174-86-3			
Coumaphos	56-72-4			
Diazinon	333-41-5			
Dichlorvos	62-73-7			
Dicrotophos	141-66-2			
DIMET (Dimethoate)	60-51-5			
Disulfoton	298-04-4			
DMDTP (Dimethyl dithiophosphate)	70577-78-5			
DMP (Dimethyl phosphate)	813-78-5			
DMTP (Dimethyl thiophosphate)	1112-38-5			
Ethion	563-12-2			
Fenitrothion	122-14-5			
Fenthion	55-38-9			
Fenthion-sulfone	3761-42-0			
Fluorodifen	15457-05-3			
IMPY (2-Isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxypyrimidine)	2814-20-2			
Malathion	121-75-5			
MDA (Malathion dicarboxylic acid)	1190-28-9			
METHA (Methamidophos)	10265-92-6			
Methidathion	950-37-8			
MNP (3-Methyl-4-nitrophenol)	2581-34-2			
Monocrotophos	6923-22-4			
OMET (Omethoate)	1113-02-6			
Paraoxon	311-45-5			
Parathion	56-38-2			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

12. Pesticides-organophosphorus

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Parathion-methyl	298-00-0			
Phosmet	732-11-6			
PNP (p-Nitrophenol)	100-02-7			
Pyrazophos	13457-18-6			
Chorpyrifos	2921-88-2			
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	5598-13-0			
DEAMPY (2-Diethylamino-6-methyl-4-pyrimidinol)	42487-72-9			
DEDTP (Diethyldithiophosphate)	298-06-6			
DEP (Diethyl phosphate)	598-02-7			
DETP (Diethyl thiophosphate)	5871-17-0			
Pirimiphos-methyl	29232-93-7			
TCPy (3,5,6-Trichloro-2-pyridinol)	6515-38-4			
Triclopyr	55335-06-3			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

13. Pesticides-phenylpyrazole

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
Fipronil sulfone	120068-36-2			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

14. Pesticides-glyphosate

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Glyphosate	1071-83-6			
AMPA (Aminomethylyphosphonic acid)	1066-51-9			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

15. Pesticides-organochlorine

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
ALAM (Alochlor mercapturate)	116482-92-9			
Aldrin	309-00-2			
Alachlor	15972-60-8			
Atrazine	1912-24-9			
ATZM (Atrazine mercapturate)	138722-96-0			
Chlordane	12789-03-6			
Chlordecone	143-50-0			
Dieldrin	60-57-1			
Endrin	128-10-9			
HCB (Hexachlorobenzene)	118-74-1			
Heptachlor	76-44-8			
Heptachlor epoxide	1024-57-3			
Methoxychlor	72-43-5			
METM (Metolachlor mercapturate)	159956-64-6			
Metolachlor	51218-45-2			
MIREX (Dodecacloropentaciclodecano)	2385-85-5			
o,p'-DDD (o,p'-Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethane)	92288-93-2			
o,p'-DDE (o,p'-Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene)	3424-82-6			
o,p'-DDT (o,p'-Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane)	789-02-6			
o,p'-Dicofol	10606-46-9			
p,p'-DDE (p,p'-Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene)	72-55-9			
p,p'-DDT (p,p'-Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane)	50-29-3			
p,p'-DDD (p,p'-Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethane)	72-54-8			
p,p'-Dicofol	115-32-2			
Toxaphene	8001-35-2			
2,4-DCP (2,4-Dichlorophenol)	120-83-2			
2,4-D (2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid)	94-75-7			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

15. Pesticides-organochlorine

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
2,4,5-T (2,4,5-Trichlorophenoxyacetic acid)	93-76-5			
2,5-DCP (2,5-Dichlorophenol)	583-78-8			
α -Endosulfan	959-98-8			
β -Endosulfan	33213-65-9			
α -HCH (α -Hexachlorocyclohexane)	319-84-6			
β -HCH (β -Hexachlorocyclohexane)	319-85-7			
γ -HCH (γ -Hexachlorocyclohexane)	58-89-9			
δ -HCH (δ -Hexachlorocyclohexane)	319-86-8			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

16. Pesticides-neonicotinoids

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Acetamiprid	135410-20-7			
N-desmethylacetamiprid	190604-92-3			
Clothianidin	210880-92-5			
Dinotefuran	165252-70-0			
Imidacloprid	138261-41-3			
Nitenpyram	150824-47-8			
Thiacloprid	111988-49-9			
Thiamethoxam	153719-23-4			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

17. Pesticides-other

Biomarkers <i>Please add</i>	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>

2. Experience in chemical analysis

18. Aprotic solvents

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
AMCC (N-Acetyl-S-(N-methylcarbamoyl)cysteine)	103974-29-4			
AMMA (S-(Acetamidomethyl) mercapturic acid)				
DMAC-OH (N-Hydroxymethyl-N-methylacetamide)				
NMAC, NMA (N-Methylacetamide)	79-16-3			
NMF (N-Methylformamide)	123-39-7			
2-HESI (2-Hydroxy-N-ethylsuccinimide)	18190-44-8			
2-HMSI (2-Hydroxy-N-methylsuccinimide)	5343-69-1			
5-HNEP (5-Hydroxy-N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone)	72954-65-5			
5-HNMP (5-Hydroxy-N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone)	41194-00-7			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

19. UV filters-benzophenones

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
BP1 (Benzophenone-1)	131-56-6			
BP2 (Benzophenone-2)	131-55-5			
BP3 (Benzophenone-3)	131-57-7			
BP6 (Benzophenone-6)	131-54-4			
BP7 (Benzophenone-7)	85-19-8			
BP8 (Benzophenone-8)	131-53-3			
4HBP (Hydroxybenzophenone)	1137-42-4			
4MP (Methylbenzophenone)	134-84-9			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

20. Diisocyanates

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
HDA (1,6-Hexamethylenediamine)	124-09-4			
MDA (4,4'-Methylenedianiline)	101-77-9			
MDI-Lysine				
MDI-Val				
NDA (1,5-Naphthylenediamine)	2243-62-1			
2,4 TDA (2,4-Toluenediamine)	95-80-7			
2,4 TDI-lysine (2,4-Toluenediisocyanate lysine)				
2,6 TDA (2,6-Toluenediamine)	823-40-5			
2,6 TDI-lysine (2,6-Toluenediisocyanate lysine)				

2. Experience in chemical analysis

21. Aromatic amines

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Acetanilide, N-Phenylacetamide	103-84-4			
Aniline	62-53-3			
m-Chloroaniline	108-42-9			
m-Fluoroaniline	372-19-0			
N-Acetyl 4,4'-methylenebis (2-chloroaniline)	91575-28-9			
N-Acetyl-2-aminophenol	614-80-2			
N-Acetyl-4-aminophenol, paracetamol	103-90-2			
o-Chloroaniline	95-51-2			
o-Fluoroaniline	348-54-9			
o-Toluidine	95-53-4			
p-Aminophenol	123-30-8			
p-Chloroaniline	106-47-8			
p-Fluoroaniline	371-40-4			
p-Toluidine	106-49-0			
1,4-Phenylenediamine	106-50-3			
2-Methoxyaniline	90-04-0			
2-Methylaniline	95-53-4			
2,3-Dichloroaniline	608-27-5			
2,4-Diaminotoluene	95-80-7			
2,4-Dichloroaniline	554-00-7			
2,4-Toluenediamine	95-80-7			
2,5-Dichloroaniline	95-82-9			
2,5-Toluenediamine	95-70-5			
2,6-Diaminotoluene	823-40-5			
2,6-Dichloroaniline	608-31-1			
2,6-Diisopropylaniline	24544-04-5			
2,6-Toluenediamine	823-40-5			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

21. Aromatic amines

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose:</i> Yes No	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose:</i> ng/mL ng/g
3-Aminobiphenyl	2243-47-2			
3-Trifluoromethylaniline	98-16-8			
3,4-Dichloroaniline	95-76-1			
3,5-Dichloroaniline	626-43-7			
4-Aminobiphenyl	92-67-1			
4-Ethylaniline	589-16-2			
4-Isopropylaniline	99-88-7			
4-Methylaniline	106-49-0			
4-Methyl-m-phenylenediamine/p-Phenylenediamine	106-50-3			
4-Trifluoromethylaniline	455-14-1			
4,4'-Methylenebis(2-chloroaniline)	101-14-4			
4,4'-Methylenedianiline	101-77-9			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

22. Parabens

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Benzylparaben	94-18-8			
Ethylparaben	120-47-8			
Isobutylparaben	4247-02-3			
Isopropylparaben	4191-73-5			
Methylparaben	99-76-3			
n-Butylparaben	94-26-8			
n-Propylparaben	94-13-3			
PHBA (p-hydroxy-benzoic acid)	99-96-7			
PHHA (p-hydroxy-hippuric acid)	2482-25-9			
Triclosan	3380-34-5			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

23. Dioxins and Furans

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
Bergamottin	482-46-2			
DCDD (2,7-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin)	33857-26-0			
Furan	110-00-9			
Furosemide	54-31-9			
L-739,010				
L-754,394	160729-91-9			
MCDD (2-Chlorodibenzo-p-dioxin)	39227-54-8			
Menthofuran	494-90-6			
Methfuroxam	28730-17-8			
PCDD 10 (2,3-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin)	29446-15-9			
PCDD 3 (1,2-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin)	54536-18-4			
PCDD 5 (1,4-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin)	54536-19-5			
PCDD 54 (1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin)	40321-76-4			
Prazosin	19216-56-9			
TCDD (2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin)	1746-01-6			
Teucrin A	12798-51-5			
1,3-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin	50585-39-2			
1,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin	50585-46-1			
1,6-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin	38178-38-0			
2-Methylfuran	534-22-5			
2-(N-ethylcarbamoyl-hydroxymethyl)-furan				
2,3-Dibromo-7,8-dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin	50585-40-5			
2,3,4,7,8-PentaCDF (2,3,4,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran)	57117-31-4			
2,3,7-Trichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin	33857-28-2			
2,3,7,8-TetraCDF (2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzofuran)	51207-31-9			
2,8-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin	38964-22-6			
3-Methylfuran	930-27-8			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

23. Dioxins and Furans

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
4-Ipomeanol	32954-58-8			
7,8-Dichlorodibenzo-p-dioxin-2-ol	97741-80-5			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

24. Musks

Biomarkers	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL ng/g</i>
ADBI (4-Acetyl-1,1-dimethyl-6-tert-butyl indane)	13171-00-1			
AHDI (6-Acetyl-1,1,2,3,3,5-hexamethyl indane)	15323-35-0			
AHTN (7-Acetyl-1,1,3,4,4,6-hexamethyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene)	85549-79-7			
ATII (5-Acetyl-1,1,2,6-tetramethyl-3-isopropyl indane)	68140-48-7			
HHCB (1,3,4,6,7,8-Hexahydro-4,6,6,7,8,8-hexamethylcyclopenta-(γ)-2-benzopyran)	1222-05-5			
HHCB-lactone (4,6,6,7,8,8-Hexamethyl-1H,3H,4H,6H,7H, 8H-indeno[5,6-c]pyran-1-one)				
Musk ambrette (1-Tert-butyl-2-methoxy-4-methyl-3,5-dinitrobenzene)	83-66-9			
Musk ketone (4-Tert-butyl-3,5-dinitro-2,6-dimethylacetophenone)	81-14-1			
Musk moskene (1,1,3,3,5-Pentamethyl-4,6-dinitroindane)	116-66-5			
Musk T (1,4-Dioxacycloheptadecane-5,17-dione)	105-95-3			
Musk tibetene (1-Tert-butyl-3,4,5-trimethyl-2,6-dinitrobenzene)	145-39-1			
Musk xylene (1-Tert-butyl-3,5-dimethyl-2,4,6-trinitrobenzene)	81-15-2			
OTNE (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-Octahydro-2,3,8,8-tetramethylnaphthalen-2yl)ethan-1-one)	54464-57-2			
6,7-Dihydro-1,1,2,3,3-pentamethyl-4(5H)-indanon	33704-61-9			

2. Experience in chemical analysis

25. Other chemicals

Biomarkers <i>Please add</i>	CAS number	Analysed <i>Please choose: Yes No</i>	LOQ (value)	LOQ (units) <i>Please choose: ng/mL na/a</i>

3. Correction measures (Adjustment)

Question	Answer
3.1 Do you have experience in the analysis of creatinine in urine?	Yes/No
3.1.1 Do you participate in any proficiency test for creatinine analysis?	Yes/No
3.1.2 If yes, please specify in which one	
3.2 Do you have experience in the determination of specific gravity?	Yes/No
3.3 Do you have experience in the analysis of lipids in blood?	Triglycerides (TG) Cholesterol (CHOL) Phospholipids (PL)

4. Participation in proficiency tests (PTs participation)

Question	Answer
4.1 Do you participate in proficiency tests (PTs) on a regular basis?	Yes/No
4.1.1 Please indicate the programmes in which you usually participate:	CTQ-INSPQ, QMEQAS (Quebec Multielement External Quality Assessment Scheme) CTQ-INSPQ, OSEQAS (External Quality Assessment Scheme for Organic Substances in Urine) CTQ-INSPQ, Creatinine (Interlaboratory Comparison Program for Measurement of Serum Creatinine) CTQ-INSPQ, Dioxin Furans (Interlaboratory Comparison Program for Dioxin Furans in Serum) CTQ-INSPQ, PCI (Interlaboratory Comparison Program for Metals in Biological Matrices) CTQ-INSPQ, AMAP (AMAP Ring Test for Persistent Organic Pollutants in Human Serum) G-EQUAS (The German External Quality Assessment Scheme) Other, please specify
4.2 Are you interested in participating in the PARC QA/QC programme?	Yes/No

5. Experience in organising PTs (Experience_PT organization)

Question	Answer
5.1 Do you have experience in organizing proficiency tests (PTs)?	Yes/No
5.1.1 Please, specify in which groups of chemicals:	Acrylamide Aprotic solvents Aromatic amines Bisphenols Cotinine Diisocyanates DINH Dioxins Flame retardants Furans Metals and trace elements Musks Mycotoxins Parabens Pesticides Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) Phthalates Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) UV filters-benzophenones Others, please specify
5.1.2 Please, indicate in what human matrices:	adipose tissue breast milk cord blood faeces dried blood spot samples (DBS) hair meconium nails placenta plasma

5. Experience in organising PTs (Experience_PT organization)

	saliva semen serum urine volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMs) whole blood others
5.1.3 How many PTs rounds per year could you organise?	Number
5.1.4 What is the average number of participants in each round?	Number
5.2 Is your laboratory accredited by the UNE-EN ISO/IEC 17043 standard?	Yes/No

6. Harmonization activities under Task 9.3

Question	Answer
<i>To finish the questionnaire, we kindly ask you to answer some questions that will support the harmonization activities under Task 9.3</i>	
6.1 Which definition of LOQ do you use?	
6.2 How do you determine the method LOQ in your lab?	
6.3 For identification when using LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS methods:	
6.3.1 How many transitions/ions do you use for compound identification?	
6.3.2 What is your acceptance criterion for retention time?	
6.3.3 What is your acceptance criterion for the ion ratio?	